

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF MODERN EDUCATION - A PARADIGM AS ONE OF THE GOALS CHANGES

Kurbanov Ikhtiyor Hikmatovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali Ibn Sino, department of "Pedagogy.

Psychology and Languages",

ihti07@mail.ru, ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3353-571X>

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the consideration of theoretical aspects of studying the psychological readiness of teachers for innovative activities. Psychological and pedagogical studies devoted to the study of this phenomenon are analyzed. An attempt has been made to identify the structure of the teacher's psychological readiness for innovative activity, which will make it possible to determine and develop psychological and pedagogical technologies for its formation among teachers. The concept "innovations" and the maintenance of innovations of the higher education is analyzed in the article.*

Keywords: *education, reforms, innovation, J. Dewey, business, training methods.*

Since the introduction of the Uzbek higher education system to the Bologna process, teachers and administrative staff from education have been paying close attention to innovations and their application. Disputes about this are the most fierce. Conferences, seminars, round tables, meetings of ministries and departments involved in innovative topics are organized; plans, strategic directions and practical recommendations for the implementation of innovative projects are created. The range of discussions is very wide: from complete rejection of any innovations in the field of education to full active immersion in innovative teaching methods, accompanied by calls to forget traditional forms and methods of education in the form of lectures, theoretical seminars and explanations from the teacher.

Although not always an active position corresponds to the very concept of "innovation" and its essential characteristics. This circumstance requires, firstly, an appeal to the origins of the concept of "innovation" and, secondly, the study of the approbation of this phenomenon in the early models of American and Western European education. If we consider innovations in the sense of actively introducing new, creative teaching methods into the educational process, then, oddly enough, it is worth moving from the field of education to the field of entrepreneurship. It was in entrepreneurial activity that the Austrian theorist J. Schumpeter began to consider innovation as a system of new combinations, new ideas and activities, and the innovator as a creator, a creative person whose motives will give joy to himself and to those who will use the results of his work. Schumpeter noted: "The task of entrepreneurs is to reform and revolutionize the way of production by introducing inventions, and in a general sense – through the use of new technologies for the production of new goods or former goods, but by a new method, thanks to the discovery of a new source of raw materials or a new market for finished products – up to the reorganization of the former and the creation of a new industry ..." [1. p. 302]. The teacher should be ready to constantly search and find new teaching methods that will meet the needs of society and the needs of categories of students. In the guidance documents of the Ministry of Education of the Uzbek Republic after the signing of the Bologna Convention, this approach is designated as a transition from an explanatory model of education based on the translation of knowledge to a competence model. A significant part of the latter is occupied by the process of

forming the skills and abilities of graduates of schools and universities to survive in a socially, economically and politically complex structured society. On the one hand, awareness of the future problems that a future graduate will face contributes to the introduction of new subjects, the creation of new teaching methods, the formulation of new, large-scale tasks in education, the final result of which should be the preparation of a person for effective and productive activities in various socially significant situations. In modern state educational standards, this readiness is designated as competencies, about which endless discussions are conducted, since there is no unambiguous definition of the essence of this category. Most often, competence is considered as "actions, understanding of the problem, analysis, search for solutions and activities to solve the problem and achieve a result" [2, p. 19;]. On the other hand, the desire to replace the old paradigm with innovations can also have negative social consequences. Based on the basic concepts of the Bologna model, some researchers believe that the former education is not only outdated, but it is, no less, "aimed mainly at the development of intelligence as the main condition for individual and social development, while other resources of human and human evolution are not involved in it" But the question arises: is it not the development of intelligence, if this concept is understood as "the ability to create", that all modern educational reforms in Uzbekistan are striving for? If this is not the case, then logically it should be recognized that there is something else behind the reforms that is deeply hidden from the consciousness of the layman who wants to get a quality education for himself and his children. The desire to avoid the explanatory paradigm as much as possible, as one of the goals of innovative changes, is already reflected in the quality of education in the form of a reduction in hours for studying not only "ineffective" humanities, but also fundamental, natural science disciplines that create "excess knowledge"; a decrease in students' motivation for independent work, a drop in the level of education of school graduates and, accordingly, there is a decrease in the requirements for applicants to universities, a drop in constructive thinking, a deterioration in operating with existing knowledge, etc. In 2016, according to the results of inspections in the country's schools, 55% of second grade students could not make a sentence out of the given words. The problems of higher education in recent years have become the subject field of numerous discussions. Particular emphasis is placed on the introduction of new teaching methods, which are designed to compensate for the helplessness of students and teachers in the face of constant reforms in education, which are criticized both by the pedagogical community and by state officials, who are forced to admit that over the years of reforms, Uzbek secondary and higher education has lost its leading positions in many areas: mathematics, physics, engineering and others. Schoolchildren, and then students, can reproduce knowledge, but they cannot explain it. Obviously, the desire of the reformers of the 2000s to bring Uzbek education under universal models (foresight "Education-2030", "Global Universities", "Dublin descriptors", etc.) led to the deprivation of its basic foundations, the destruction of classical foundations, the destruction of traditional attitudes and the replacement of these values with market, more precisely, service services. In such a situation, every socially responsible teacher and researcher is forced to seek a compromise between "effective competencies" tuned to market profit, the social consequences of the transition to a new paradigm of education and awareness of the need to maintain the actual quality of education. Thus, the analysis of only a part of the general problems of innovative transformations leads us to the conclusion that there is a need for a balanced approach to the ongoing changes in the Uzbek education system. The same conclusion applies to the

technologies used, many of which, for all their advantages, cannot replace a teacher in a lecture and seminar audience.

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